

 Organize a congress

Prerequisite:
Fame > 4 and
1 Invited speaker or
1 Foreign teaching
Donate 1 invited
speaker to other 2
players.
Fame: 4

 Best research award

Prerequisite:
Fame > 40 or at least
4 shared projects

Fame: 4

 Retraction

Play this card
when a review is
going to hit you.

You (and only you)
will not lose
Fame.

 Organize a congress

Prerequisite:
Fame > 4 and
1 Invited speaker or
1 Foreign teaching
Donate 1 invited
speaker to other 2
players.
Fame: 4

 Metadata

Put it on a Project.
If closed, it becomes
open.
You can put an
Article on this card.

Fame: 2

 Invited speaker

Prerequisite:
at least 2 Articles

Fame: 2

 Invited speaker

Prerequisite:
at least 2 Articles

Fame: 2

 Metadata

Put it on a Project.
If closed, it becomes
open.
You can put an
Article on this card.

Fame: 2

 European project

Prerequisite:
Fame >= 20

Fame 4
Gain an upgrade
Draw 1 card more
in this turn

